

History of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in Indonesia: Factors involved in outbreaks in Lampung Bay

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Abstract

In Indonesia, the world's largest island nation, HABs have been observed since the 1970s, where blooms often occur in eutrophic waters surrounding large population centres (e.g., Ambon Bay, Jakarta Bay, and Lampung Bay). Lampung Bay, in particular, has undergone extensive development and is a major economic hub, hosting a large port and a significant aquaculture industry. *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* blooms have been recorded in the inner-middle bay and Legundi Island, in the southern part of the bay. Here, we analyse the monitoring data of *M. polykrikoides* blooms in Lampung Bay from 2012 to 2020 using multivariate analysis (distance-based redundancy analysis). Outbreaks have caused mortality of caged fish including cobia (*Rachycentron canadum*; at low bloom density; from 10^3 to 10^4 cells L^{-1}), pomfret (*Trachinotus blochii*; moderate bloom; 10^5 cells L^{-1}), and grouper (*Cromileptes altivelis*, *Epinephelus fuscoguttatus*, and *E. lanceolatus*; dense bloom; $>10^5$ cells L^{-1}). Bloom density was strongly correlated with salinity and phosphate (DIP) concentration ($P < 0.05$), where dense blooms (from 1.68×10^7 to 4.70×10^7 cells L^{-1}) were associated with high DIP (7 - 12 μM) and moderate to high blooms (from 4.34×10^5 to 4.81×10^6 cells L^{-1}) associated with higher salinity (31.8 - 32). In addition, low (from 1.45×10^3 to 2.81×10^4 cells L^{-1}) and moderate (from 3.1×10^4 to 9.5×10^4 cells L^{-1}) bloom density may be influenced by high nitrate, DO, pH, and temperature ($P < 0.05$). At moderate salinity (31.3 - 31.6), the blooms showed that nitrate and DIP are the dominant macronutrient that limits overall *M. polykrikoides* density in the bay. This study suggests that *M. polykrikoides* blooms in Lampung Bay under wide environmental conditions but that cell densities may be regulated by nutrient availability.

Keywords: *Margalefidinium polykrikoides*, ichthyotoxic, eutrophication, aquaculture, distance-based redundancy analysis (db-RDA)

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Introduction

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) have been observed in Indonesia since the 1970s. Blooms often occur in waters surrounding large population centres that have experienced eutrophication (e.g., Ambon Bay, Jakarta Bay, and Lampung Bay). Eutrophication is one of several factors (besides hydrodynamics and weather conditions) that leads to more frequent and extensive HABs globally (Anderson *et al.*, 2002, 2012; Damar *et al.*, 2021) including those considered toxic or harmful, can be natural phenomena, the nature of the global problem of harmful algal blooms (HABs).

Margalefidinium polykrikoides outbreaks have exclusively been observed in Lampung Bay. Anthropogenic activities, such as waste water discharge, shipping, and aquaculture, has led to the accumulation of nutrients in Lampung Bay (Damar *et al.*, 2012) that have coincided with more extensive outbreaks of *M. polykrikoides* (expanding to Legundi Island, the southern part of the bay in 2020; Muawanah and Garbono, 2020). Blooms have caused a decline in aquaculture enterprises from 150 farms in 2010 to 26 in 2018 (Muawanah *et al.*, 2018). In this study, we assess monitoring data of *M. polykrikoides* outbreaks in Lampung Bay to investigate the regulation of bloom density by nutrient availability.

Material and Methods

Study Area

Lampung Bay (5° 26' S - 5° 50' S, 105° 10' E - 105° 35' E; Fig. 1), is a shallow water bay (17.6 m mean depth) located in south-

eastern Sumatra (Wiryawan *et al.*, 1999). The tidal pattern is semi-diurnal, influenced by the water mass from the Indian Ocean that is transported through the Sunda strait (Helfinalis, 2000; Wiryawan *et al.*, 1999). The nutrient load in Lampung Bay is 5002.8 t DIN y⁻¹, 1095.56 t PO₄-P y⁻¹ and 14731.5 t SiO₄ y⁻¹ with a relatively long water residence time of 15 days, in comparison to Jakarta that has a shorter water residence time (five days; Damar *et al.*, 2012).

Fig. 1. *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* bloom locations from 2012 to 2020 and main anthropogenic activities in Lampung Bay (modified from Thoha *et al.*, 2019)

In addition to land runoff and anthropogenic activities, nutrient input to Lampung Bay is influenced by oceanographic circulation patterns. During the Northwest monsoon (rainy season) nutrient levels in the mouth of the Kota Karang and Way Lunik rivers and the inner part of the bay are elevated. In

contrast, during the Southeast (SE) monsoon (dry season), the nutrients in the middle and outer part of the bay show a high value due to nutrient-enriched water masses from Java Island that come through the Sunda Strait into the Bay (Damar *et al.*, 2014, 2012).

These nutrient inputs support high primary productivity in Lampung Bay with an annual primary production ranging from 31 to 196 g C m⁻² y⁻¹ (Damar *et al.*, 2014, 2012), which is suitable for aquaculture. However, the bay is susceptible to HABs. Outbreaks of *Alexandrium* sp., *Ceratium furca*, *Chaetoceros socialis*, *Dynophysis caudata*, *Gymnodinium* sp., *M. polykrikoides*, *Noctiluca scintillans*, *Ostreopsis* sp., *Prorocentrum* sp., *Protoperidinium* sp., *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Pyrodinium bahamense*, and *Trichodesmium* sp. have been reported to occur in Lampung Bay since 2012 (Muawanah unpublished data, 2020).

Monitoring activity

Water quality monitoring has been conducted frequently since 2012 based on reports of blooms in aquaculture areas. Monitoring involved measuring the surface water (turbidity, dissolved oxygen, temperature, and salinity), dissolved nutrients (ammonium, nitrate, nitrite, total DIN, phosphate (DIP)), and phytoplankton density. Dominant phytoplankton found in surface water preserved in Lugol solution (Edler and Elbrächter, 2010) were identified and enumerated under a light microscope (Zeiss, Germany).

Data Analysis

Blooms of *M. polykrikoides* recorded in six locations (Pasaran Island, Hurun Bay, Ringgung, Ratai Bay, Tarahan, and Legundi

Island; figure 1) during 2012-2020 were analysed. To determine the association between environmental parameters and *M. polykrikoides* bloom density, distance-based redundancy analysis (db-RDA) was undertaken. Blooms with incomplete water quality data were excluded from the analysis, leaving 27 samples from five locations (excluding Legundi Island) in the dataset. Kruskal-Wallis statistical tests (significance level $P < 0.05$) were used to assess whether the variation between stations and seasons was significant. Species data were square-root transformed, and all the explanatory variables (environmental parameters) were standardised. The db-RDA reduced model was obtained by subjecting the db-RDA full model to *posthoc* analysis by a variance inflation factor (VIF) to detect multicollinearity within explanatory variables. Explanatory variables with a VIF value > 10 (showing collinearity with other variables) were removed in the reduced db-RDA model, and Monte-Carlo permutations were run to test the model's significance. The most significant explanatory variables in db-RDA best model were observed by obtaining stepwise selection of environmental variables. The db-RDA and its *posthoc* analysis were performed using the “vegan” package in R (Zuur *et al.*, 2007; Borcard *et al.*, 2011).

Results and Discussion

A total of 63 *M. polykrikoides* outbreaks were recorded in Lampung Bay from 2012 to 2020. Blooms were frequently observed in the northern inner bay waters within Hurun Bay (38 events) and Pasaran Island (13 events). However, there was no distinct variation (Kruskal Wallis, $P > 0.05$) in bloom occurrence, mean bloom density, and mean

bloom duration across spatial and temporal scales, meaning *M. polykrikoides* outbreaks arise throughout Lampung Bay and may occur throughout the year.

Table 1. Summary of *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* bloom conditions in Lampung Bay

Variable	Min	Max	Average \pm SD	Limit*
Bloom density (cells L ⁻¹)	1.45 x 10 ³	4.70 x 10 ⁷	4.40 x 10 ⁶ \pm 1.27 x 10 ⁷	-
Bloom duration (weeks)	1.0	3.7	1.7 \pm 1.0	-
Temperature (°C)	28.45	31.38	29.90 \pm 0.70	-
Salinity (ppt)	28.50	33.00	31.37 \pm 0.90	30 - 34
Nitrate (μ M)	0.98	42.20	14.62 \pm 8.82	0.13
Ammonium (μ M)	0.47	52.28	10.72 \pm 10.89	8.81
Phosphate (μ M)	0.15	40.72	3.65 \pm 7.54	0.12

*Threshold of water quality defined by Minister of Environment and Forestry in Ministerial Decree (No. 51, 2004, Indonesia).

Overall, nutrient concentrations during outbreaks were higher than the regulated threshold (Table 1). The outbreaks often occurred in the afternoon after one day of heavy rains, which were marked by brownish water discolorations and fish mortality (Muawanah *et al.*, 2015). In addition, caged fish killed during mortality events included cobia (*Rachycentron canadum*) at low-density blooms (10³-10⁴ cells L⁻¹), pomfret (*Trachinotus blochii*) during moderate-blooms (10⁵ cells L⁻¹) and grouper (*Cromileptes altivelis*, *Epinephelus fuscoguttatus* and *E. lanceolatus*) during dense blooms (>10⁵ cells L⁻¹), all with excessive mucus on their gills (Muawanah *et al.*, 2013).

Based on the db-RDA best model ($P < 0.05$; data not shown), salinity and phosphate (DIP) were the two most significant explanatory variables (with an r-square value of 22%) that appeared to influence the distribution of *M. polykrikoides* bloom density in Lampung Bay. Moreover, the db-RDA reduced model ($P < 0.05$; Fig. 2) showed the inclusion of other environmental parameters (ammonium, nitrate, DO, pH, and temperature) increased the r-square value to 42%.

Fig. 2. Ordination of reduced db-RDA model ($P < 0.05$) on *M. polykrikoides* bloom abundance in Lampung Bay using only explanatory variables with VIF value < 10 . Green lines show phosphate (DIP) distributions; Yellow lines show nitrate distribution; ** 0.05; * 0.01.

Thus, the ordination indicates that dense blooms ($1.68 \times 10^7 - 4.70 \times 10^7$ cells L⁻¹) in Q4 correlates with high DIP (7-12 μ M; Fig. 2) and moderate to high blooms ($4.34 \times 10^5 - 4.81 \times 10^6$ cells L⁻¹) in Q3 correlates with high salinity (31.8-32; Fig. 2). In addition, low ($1.45 \times 10^3 - 2.81 \times 10^4$ cells L⁻¹) and moderate ($3.1 \times 10^4 - 9.5 \times 10^4$ cells L⁻¹) bloom density observed in Q1 and Q2, respectively, may

be influenced by high nitrate, DO, pH, and temperature.

Interestingly, in Q2 and Q4, where the salinity was moderate (ranging from 31.3-31.6 (data not shown), indicative of freshwater runoff), the bloom density seemed to be driven by different factors, high nitrate (15.5-16 μM) in Q2 and high DIP (7-12 μM) in Q4, with the bloom density tending to be lower in Q2 than in Q4. This suggests that nitrate and DIP are the dominant macronutrients that limit overall *M. polykrikoides* density in the bay.

Although our statistical analysis showed no significant difference across location and season, most of the bloom outbreaks under high nitrate (Q2) occurred during the dry season (Southeast (SE) monsoon), with the nutrient source likely being nutrient-enriched water masses that are transported through the Sunda Strait into the Bay, as well as the aquaculture activities observed in this location (Sachoemar *et al.*, 2005; Damar *et al.*, 2012, 2014). Conversely, blooms under high DIP (Q4) were observed during the rainy season (Northwest (NW) monsoon) with nutrients sourced from the Kota Karang and Way Lunik rivers.

Apart from nutrients however, there are other factors (e.g., ecological interactions such as grazing) that were not measured in this study that may help to explain bloom variance. For example, the relative abundance of HAB species within a phytoplankton community is an important context for the competitive success of HABs (Wells *et al.*, 2020). Thus, *M. polykrikoides* abundance as a proportion of the overall phytoplankton biomass may potentially influence the timing and progression of blooms. Furthermore, the

high density of *M. polykrikoides* cysts in the sediment collected at Hurun Bay and Pasaran Island (166.1 and 645.6 cysts g^{-1} dw, respectively; Thoha *et al.*, 2019) may also contribute to inducing high bloom occurrence in these locations (Anderson, 1998).

Given the detrimental consequences of *M. polykrikoides* blooms on caged fish, nutrient management is essential for the sustainability of food production in Lampung Bay. Further studies should involve phytoplankton community and toxicity assessment and ecological processes during bloom and non-bloom periods.

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